

Supplementary Materials

Population Size Differences Can Lead to Biases in Phylogenetic Inference and Introgression Detection in the Presence of Purifying Selection

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Supplementary Methods

Examining the Values of $P(V_1 | V)$ under Neutral Evolution and under Purifying Selection

$P(V_1 | V)$ is the probability that a genealogical tree is a type V_1 genealogical tree given that this genealogical tree is a type V genealogical tree (Fig. 7). Under neutral evolution, it is theoretically expected that $P(V_1 | V) = 2/3$ (Fig. 9B, Supplementary Appendix 2). The SLiM simulation described here aimed to empirically examine whether $P(V_1 | V)$ is indeed $2/3$ under evolution. We also examined whether the value of $P(V_1 | V)$ under purifying selection is greater or smaller than that under neutral evolution. We set the simplest biallelic context in our simulations because our aim was to determine the direction (greater or smaller) of the difference between the values of $P(V_1 | V)$ under purifying selection and under neutral evolution. If more than two alleles are involved, the magnitude of the difference can change, nevertheless, but the direction of the difference will not change. The “Mutation.time” and “Mutation.node” attributes in the Python package tskit were used to extract information about the time each mutation occurs and the branch each mutation falls on. We analyzed gene trees that experienced deep coalescence and at the same time contained one and only one mutation occurring at a time earlier than time t_{123} (this mutation corresponds to the mutation M in our theoretical analysis). Among these gene trees, we calculated the ratio between gene trees where the mutation occurring in S_{123} falls on the first diverging branch (type V_1) and gene trees where the mutation occurring in S_{123} falls on any of three terminal branches (type V).

Supplementary Appendix S1

Here, we provide a more rigorous explanation of why under patterns A_3 , A_4 , and A_5 , $P(V_1 | A_x) = P(V_1 | V)$ ($x = 3, 4, 5$). As patterns A_3 , A_4 , and A_5 are similar, here, we take pattern A_3 as an example (g_1 and g_2 are connected to “noncarriers” and g_3 is connected to a “carrier” at t_{123} , Fig. 7). If pattern A_3 occurs, G_{123} is certainly a type V genealogical tree. Hence, $P(V_1 | A_3)$ may be written as $P(V_1 | A_3V)$. Then, according to Bayes’ theorem, $P(V_1 | A_3V)$ may be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P(V_1 | A_3) &= P(V_1 | A_3V) = \frac{P(V_1A_3|V)}{P(A_3|V)} = \frac{P(V_1A_3|V)}{P(V_1A_3|V) + P(\bar{V}_1A_3|V)} \\ &= \frac{P(V_1|V)P(A_3|V_1V)}{P(V_1|V)P(A_3|V_1V) + P(\bar{V}_1|V)P(A_3|\bar{V}_1V)} \end{aligned}$$

Biologically speaking, regardless of mediators’ genealogical positions in G_{123} (depending on evolutionary events earlier than t_{123}), “carriers” are still “carriers”, and “noncarriers” are still “noncarriers”. How g_1 , g_2 , and g_3 are connected to mediators (depending on evolutionary events latter than t_{123}) only depends on whether mediators are “carriers” or “noncarriers”. This is irrelevant to mediators’ genealogical positions of in G_{123} . This essentially is a case of the Markov property: Given the “current state” (the states of mediators at t_{123}), the “earlier state” is irrelevant to the “future state”. Accordingly,

$P(A_3|V_1V) = P(A_3|\bar{V}_1V) = P(A_3|V)$, and the above expression becomes:

$$P(V_1 | A_3) = \frac{P(V_1|V)}{P(V_1|V) + P(\bar{V}_1|V)} = P(V_1|V)$$

Following a similar logic, it can also be proven that under patterns A_6 , A_7 , and A_8 ,

$$P(W_1 | A_x) = P(W_1 | W) \quad (x = 6, 7, 8).$$

Supplementary Appendix S2

The equivalence relationship between p_i and $E(f_i)$ can be more rigorously understood as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} p_i &= P\{a_i \text{ is a "carrier"}\} \\ &= P\{g_i \text{ is a descendant of a "carrier"}\} \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P(g_i \text{ is a descendant of a "carrier" } | f_i) p(f_i) df_i \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P(\text{a descendant of a "carrier" is sampled from } S_i | f_i) p(f_i) df_i \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_i p(f_i) df_i \\ &= E(f_i) \end{aligned}$$

Where, f_i denotes the frequency of descendants of "carriers" in species S_i , $p(f_i)$ denotes the probability density function of f_i .

Additionally, it may be worth noting that the equivalence relationship between p_i and $E(f_i)$ is unaffected by the presence of mutations occurring later than t_{123} (shallow mutations). This is because shallow mutations should be considered as "random noise" relative to mutation M itself. More specifically, $P(g_i \text{ is a descendant of a "carrier" } | f_i)$ is a probability over all possible carrying states of shallow mutations:

$$\begin{aligned} &P(g_i \text{ is a descendant of a "carrier" } | f_i) \\ &= \sum_{\infty} P(g_i \text{ is a descendant of a "carrier" } | u, f_i) P(u) \end{aligned}$$

Where, u denotes each possible carrying state of shallow mutations. Therefore, $p_i/E(f_i)$ is a parameter that reflects the intrinsic property of mutation M .

Supplementary Appendix S3

Here, we prove that under a neutral evolution assumption with a constant mutation rate and a constant population size, $P(V_1 | V) = 2/3$. We use X_1 and X_2 to denote the waiting time for the first coalescent event and the waiting time for the second coalescent event, respectively (Fig. 9B). The waiting time for the first coalescent event X_1 and the waiting time for the second coalescent event X_2 follow an exponential distribution with rate parameter λ_1 and an exponential distribution with rate parameter λ_2 , respectively. The expected waiting time for the first coalescent event and that for the second coalescent event are $1/\lambda_1$ and $1/\lambda_2$, respectively. Let R denote the ratio distribution of X_2 to X_1 , i.e., $R = X_2/X_1$. As the first and the second coalescent events are mutually independent, the probability density function of R is as follows (Blom 1989):

$$f(r) = \begin{cases} \int_0^{\infty} x_1 \cdot \lambda_1 e^{-\lambda_1 x_1} \cdot \lambda_2 e^{-\lambda_2 (r x_1)} dx_1, & r > 0 \\ 0, & \text{others} \end{cases}$$

When $r > 0$, $f(r)$ may be simplified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(r) &= \int_0^{\infty} x_1 \cdot \lambda_1 e^{-\lambda_1 x_1} \cdot \lambda_2 e^{-\lambda_2 (r x_1)} dx_1 \\ &= \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \int_0^{\infty} x_1 \cdot e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 r) x_1} dx_1 \\ &= \frac{\lambda_1 \lambda_2}{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 r)^2} \Gamma(2) \end{aligned}$$

Above, $\Gamma(2)$ is a gamma function, which is equal to 1. Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} f(r) &= \frac{\lambda_1 \lambda_2}{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 r)^2} \\ &= \frac{\lambda_1 / \lambda_2}{(\lambda_1 / \lambda_2 + r)^2} \end{aligned}$$

In a three-tip genealogical tree, the length of the first diverging branch is $X_1 + X_2$. The total length of the three terminal branches is $3X_1 + X_2$. If mutation M falls on one of the three

terminal branches, the three-tip genealogical tree is a type V genealogical tree. Among the three terminal branches, if mutation M falls on the first diverging branch, the three-tip genealogical tree is a type V_1 genealogical tree (Fig. 9B). Therefore, let φ denote the conditional value of $P(V_1 | V)$ given that the values of X_1 and X_2 are $X_1 = x_1$ and $X_2 = x_2$, respectively. Assuming a constant mutation rate, φ is as follows:

$$\varphi = \frac{x_1 + x_2}{3x_1 + x_2} = \frac{1 + r}{3 + r}$$

Then, the overall value of $P(V_1 | V)$ across all possible values of X_1 and X_2 may be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P(V_1|V) &= \int_0^{\infty} \varphi(r)f(r)dr \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{1+r}{3+r}\right) \left[\frac{\lambda_1/\lambda_2}{(\lambda_1/\lambda_2+r)^2}\right] dr \\ &= (\lambda_1/\lambda_2) \int_0^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{2}{3+r}\right) \left[\frac{1}{(\lambda_1/\lambda_2+r)^2}\right] dr \\ &= (\lambda_1/\lambda_2) \left[\int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{(\lambda_1/\lambda_2+r)^2} dr - \int_0^{\infty} \frac{2}{(3+r)(\lambda_1/\lambda_2+r)^2} dr \right] \end{aligned}$$

Assuming a constant population size, the expected waiting time for the second coalescent event is 3 times longer than that for the first coalescent event (Kingman 1982; Tajima 1983), i.e., $\lambda_1/\lambda_2 = 3$. Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} P(V_1|V) &= (\lambda_1/\lambda_2) \left[\int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{(\lambda_1/\lambda_2+r)^2} dr - \int_0^{\infty} \frac{2}{(3+r)(\lambda_1/\lambda_2+r)^2} dr \right] \\ &= 3 \times \left[\int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{(3+r)^2} dr - \int_0^{\infty} \frac{2}{(3+r)^3} dr \right] \\ &= 3 \times \left[\frac{-1}{3+r} \Big|_0^{\infty} + \frac{1}{(3+r)^2} \Big|_0^{\infty} \right] \\ &= 3 \times \left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{9} \right) = \frac{2}{3} \end{aligned}$$

Supplementary Section S1: The Conclusion Regarding Gene Tree Distributions under Purifying Selection Remains Valid When Multiple Ancestral Mutations Are Assumed

For demonstration, in the main text, we focus on the simplest one-mutation case. Here, we show that no matter how many mutations are assumed in ancestral species S_{123} , the conclusions regarding mediators' input and output remain valid. Let us assume n mutations occurring S_{123} (n can be any integer). Then, there are $\binom{n}{n} + \binom{n}{n-1} \cdots + \binom{n}{0}$ possible allelic states. We consider an arbitrary pair of these allelic states, $type_x$ and $type_{x+k}$, where $type_x$ denotes an allelic state with a combination of x mutations, and $type_{x+k}$ denotes an allelic state where k mutations are added to $type_x$. If the mediators' output is completely random, regardless of what allelic states are $type_x$ and $type_{x+k}$, a $type_x$ gene copy should be equally likely to occupy each of the three tips of G_{123} , and a $type_{x+k}$ gene copy should also be equally likely to occupy each tip of G_{123} . The k mutations mentioned above can be viewed as a “super mutation”, and $type_x$ and $type_{x+k}$ gene copies can be viewed as “noncarriers” and “carriers”, respectively. Therefore, the effect of this “super mutation” can be understood in the same way as the effect of mutation M (Fig. 9).

Above, there are two different allelic states among the three tips of G_{123} . When more than one mutation is assumed in S_{123} , it is also possible that there are three different allelic states among the three tips of G_{123} . We now add another allelic state— $type_{x+l}$. Accordingly, $type_{x+k}$ and $type_{x+l}$ gene copies are two types of “carriers”, and $type_x$ gene copies are “noncarriers”. If there are three different allelic states among the three tips of G_{123} , there are two “super mutations” in G_{123} —one is constituted by k mutations, the other is constituted by l

mutations (see the figure below). If mediators' output is completely random, the "noncarrier" in G_{123} should be equally likely to occupy each of the three tips. That is to say, the probability that the two "super mutations" fall on the first diverging branch should be equal to the probability that they fall on one of the two nested branches (see the figure below). This conflicts with the fact that the first diverging branch is longer than the two nested branches. Therefore, gene copies at t_{123} are not equally distributed among the tips of G_{123} . Instead, it is expected that when an extant gene copy is connected to a "carrier", its connection tends to be established with the first diverging branch of G_{123} (see the figure below). This effect acts in the same direction as the effect described in the main text. Therefore, we exclude the possibility that there is a pair of effects that cancel each other out. Collectively, when multiple mutations are assumed in S_{123} , it remains biologically untenable to claim that changes in mediators' input have no effect on gene tree distributions. Furthermore, when multiple mutations are assumed, how likely g_i is connected to each type of gene copies at t_{123} (*type_x*, *type_{x-k}*, or *type_{x-k-l}*) is still determined by the expected fates of these gene copies in S_i . Therefore, regardless of how many mutations are assumed in S_{123} , it can still be concluded that, under purifying selection, population size differences can lead to changes in mediators' input, and consequently lead to changes in gene tree distributions.

Illustration of the situations where the tips of G_{123} contain three types of gene copies. A. If mediators' output is completely random, the type x gene copy (blue circle) should be equally likely to occupy each of the three possible positions. **B.** If mediators' output is completely random, the two situations shown here should be equally likely to occur, which conflicts with the fact that the first diverging branch is longer than the two nested branches. The left situation is more likely to occur than the right one. Therefore, a "noncarrier" tends to bring the gene copy connected to it to a nested branch.

Supplementary Section S2: Derivation of the Pattern of Change of Three-Taxon Gene Tree Distributions under Purifying Selection

Here, we derive the pattern of change for the probabilities of three-taxon gene tree topologies under purifying selection. For demonstration, we focus on how $P(T_1)$, $P(T_2)$, and $P(T_3)$ change as p_3 changes. For clarity, the expressions for $P(T_1)$, $P(T_2)$, and $P(T_3)$ are given below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(T_1) &= \sum_{x=1}^8 P(T_1|A_x)P(A_x) \\
 &= \frac{1}{3}q_1q_2q_3 + \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2p_3 \\
 &\quad + P(V_1|V)q_1q_2p_3 + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1p_2q_3 + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]p_1q_2q_3 \\
 &\quad + P(W_1|W)p_1p_2q_3 + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2p_3 + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2p_3 \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(T_2) &= \sum_{x=1}^8 P(T_2|A_x)P(A_x) \\
 &= \frac{1}{3}q_1q_2q_3 + \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2p_3 \\
 &\quad + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1q_2p_3 + P(V_1|V)q_1p_2q_3 + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]p_1q_2q_3 \\
 &\quad + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1p_2q_3 + P(W_1|W)p_1q_2p_3 + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2p_3 \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(T_3) &= \sum_{x=1}^8 P(T_3|A_x)P(A_x) \\
 &= \frac{1}{3}q_1q_2q_3 + \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2p_3 \\
 &\quad + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1q_2p_3 + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1p_2q_3 + P(V_1|V)p_1q_2q_3 \\
 &\quad + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1p_2q_3 + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2p_3 + P(W_1|W)q_1p_2p_3 \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

We first determine how $P(T_1)$ changes as p_3 changes by analyzing the partial derivative of $P(T_1)$ with respect to p_3 , $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3}$. According to the expression for $P(T_1)$, the expression for $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3}$ may be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3} &= -\frac{1}{3}q_1q_2 + \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2 \\
&\quad + P(V_1|V)q_1q_2 - \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 - \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 \\
&\quad + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 - P(W_1|W)p_1p_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 \\
&= \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2 + P(V_1|V)q_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 \\
&\quad - P(W_1|W)p_1p_2 - \frac{1}{3}q_1q_2 - \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 - \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 \\
&= \left[P(V_1|V) - \frac{1}{3}\right]q_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1}{3} - P(W_1|W)\right]p_1p_2 \\
&\quad + \left[\frac{P(V_1|V) - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 + \left[\frac{P(V_1|V) - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 \\
&= \left[P(V_1|V) - \frac{1}{3}\right](1 - p_1 - p_2 + p_1p_2) + \left[\frac{1}{3} - P(W_1|W)\right]p_1p_2 \\
&\quad + \left[\frac{P(V_1|V) - P(W_1|W)}{2}\right](p_1 + p_2 - 2p_1p_2) \\
&= \left[P(V_1|V) - \frac{1}{3}\right](1 - p_1 - p_2 + p_1p_2) + \left[\frac{1}{3} - P(W_1|W)\right]p_1p_2 \\
&\quad + \left[P(V_1|V) - \frac{1}{3}\right]\left(\frac{p_1 + p_2}{2} - p_1p_2\right) - \left[P(W_1|W) - \frac{1}{3}\right]\left(\frac{p_1 + p_2}{2} - p_1p_2\right) \\
&= \left[P(V_1|V) - \frac{1}{3}\right]\left(1 - \frac{p_1 + p_2}{2}\right) + \left[\frac{1}{3} - P(W_1|W)\right]\left(\frac{p_1 + p_2}{2}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

We have shown that $P(V_1 | V) \geq 2/3$ and $P(W_1 | W) = 1$ (Fig. 9). Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3} &\geq \frac{1}{3}\left(1 - \frac{p_1 + p_2}{2}\right) - \frac{2}{3}\left(\frac{p_1 + p_2}{2}\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{3} - \frac{p_1 + p_2}{2}
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

According to expression (4), if $p_1 < 1/3$ and $p_2 < 1/3$, $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3} > 0$. Now, let us consider the biological meaning of the conditions $p_1 < 1/3$ and $p_2 < 1/3$ and whether these conditions are satisfied. Let t_M denote the time at which mutation M appears in ancestral species S_{123} , and let x_M denote the total number of gene copies at time t_M . As explained in the main text, p_i is equivalent to the expected frequency of descendants of ‘‘carriers’’ in species S_i (Fig. 8). Under neutral evolution, p_i is an invariant constant and always equal to its initial frequency.

Hence, under neutral evolution, $p_i = \frac{1}{x_M}$. On the other hand, as purifying selection acts to depress the expected frequency of mutation M , under purifying selection, $p_i < \frac{1}{x_M}$. For haploid organisms, as long as the population size of S_{123} at t_M is larger than 3, $x_M > 3$; for diploid organisms, as long as the population size of S_{123} at t_M is larger than $3/2$, $x_M > 3$.

Moreover, given that deep coalescence occurs, there must exist three gene copies at time t_{123} serving as the ancestors of g_1 , g_2 , and g_3 . Therefore, except in some extremely rare situations, $p_1 < 1/3$ and $p_2 < 1/3$ are satisfied. As $p_1 < 1/3$ and $p_2 < 1/3$ are almost always satisfied, it is almost always true that $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3} > 0$, which indicates that an increase in p_3 leads to a greater $P(T_1)$. As N_3 increases, the selection effectiveness in species S_3 increases, and therefore p_3 decreases. Also note that gene copy g_3 occupies that first diverging branch of topology T_1 .

Therefore, we reach the conclusion that as N_i increases, g_i has a smaller probability of occupying the first diverging branch in gene trees (rule 1 in the main text).

The next question to consider is how the other two gene tree topologies change as p_3 changes, which can be answered by analyzing $\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3}$ and $\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3}$. The expression for $\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3}$ may be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3} &= -\frac{1}{3}q_1q_2 + \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2 \\
&+ \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] q_1q_2 - P(V_1|V)q_1p_2 - \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] p_1q_2 \\
&- \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} \right] p_1p_2 + P(W_1|W)p_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} \right] q_1p_2 \\
&= \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2 + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] q_1q_2 + P(W_1|W)p_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} \right] q_1p_2 \\
&- \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} \right] p_1p_2 - \frac{1}{3}q_1q_2 - \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] p_1q_2 - P(V_1|V)q_1p_2 \\
&= \left[\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} \right] p_1p_2 + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} - \frac{1}{3} \right] q_1q_2 \\
&+ \left[P(W_1|W) - \frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] p_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} - P(V_1|V) \right] q_1p_2 \\
&= \left[\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} \right] p_1p_2 + \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} - \frac{1}{3} \right] (1 - p_1 - p_2 + p_1p_2) \\
&+ \left[P(W_1|W) - \frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] (p_1 - p_1p_2) + \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} - P(V_1|V) \right] (p_2 - p_1p_2) \\
&= \left[\frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} - \frac{1}{3} \right] + \left[P(W_1|W) - \frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} - \frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} + \frac{1}{3} \right] p_1 \\
&+ \left[\frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} - P(V_1|V) - \frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} + \frac{1}{3} \right] p_2 \\
&+ \left[\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} + \frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} - \frac{1}{3} \right] p_1p_2 \\
&- \left[P(W_1|W) - \frac{1 - P(V_1|V)}{2} + \frac{1 - P(W_1|W)}{2} - P(V_1|V) \right] p_1p_2 \\
&= \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] + \left[P(W_1|W) + P(V_1|V) - \frac{2}{3} \right] p_1 + \left[\frac{1}{3} - \frac{P(W_1|W) + P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] p_2 \\
&= \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] + \left[\frac{P(W_1|W) + P(V_1|V)}{2} - \frac{1}{3} \right] (2p_1 - p_2) \\
&= \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] [1 - p_1 - (p_1 - p_2)] + \left[\frac{P(W_1|W)}{2} - \frac{1}{6} \right] [p_1 + (p_1 - p_2)]
\end{aligned}$$

Following the same logic, the expression for $\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3}$ may be written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3} = \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] [1 - p_2 - (p_2 - p_1)] + \left[\frac{P(W_1|W)}{2} - \frac{1}{6} \right] [p_2 + (p_2 - p_1)]$$

In summary, we have

$$\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3} = \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] [1 - p_1 - (p_1 - p_2)] + \left[\frac{P(W_1|W)}{2} - \frac{1}{6} \right] [p_1 + (p_1 - p_2)]$$

$$\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3} = \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{P(V_1|V)}{2} \right] [1 - p_2 - (p_2 - p_1)] + \left[\frac{P(W_1|W)}{2} - \frac{1}{6} \right] [p_2 + (p_2 - p_1)]$$

As $P(V_1 | V) \geq 2/3$ and $P(W_1 | W) = 1$ (Fig. 9), the expressions for $\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3}$ and $\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3}$

become as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3} &\leq \left(-\frac{1}{6} \right) [1 - p_1 - (p_1 - p_2)] + \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) [p_1 + (p_1 - p_2)] \\ &= \left(\frac{p_1}{2} - \frac{1}{6} \right) + \frac{1}{2} (p_1 - p_2) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3} \leq \left(\frac{p_2}{2} - \frac{1}{6} \right) + \frac{1}{2} (p_2 - p_1) \quad (6)$$

If $p_1 < 1/3$ and $p_2 < 1/3$, the first terms in expressions (5) and (6) are smaller than zero.

Hence, depending on whether p_1 is greater or smaller than p_2 , there is either $\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3} < 0$ or

$\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3} < 0$. Note that in gene tree topology T_2 , g_1 is the sister of g_3 , whereas in gene tree

topology T_3 , g_2 is the sister of g_3 . If N_1 is greater than N_2 , p_1 is smaller than p_2 , and then

$\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3}$ is smaller than zero; on the other hand, if N_2 is greater than N_1 , p_2 is smaller than p_1 ,

and then $\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3}$ is smaller than zero. Accordingly, if g_i does not occupy the first diverging

branch in a gene tree topology, and at the same time, the sister of g_i in this gene tree topology

is from a relatively large population, the probability of this gene tree topology always

changes in an opposite direction in comparison with the gene tree topology where g_i occupies

the first diverging branch (rule 2 in the main text). Additionally, $\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3}$ and $\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3}$ are not

necessarily both smaller than zero. Hence, the probabilities of the two gene tree topologies

where g_i does not occupy the first diverging branch do not necessarily change in the same

direction (rule 3 in the main text).

The above conclusions can be verified by the analysis shown below. An increase in p_3

means that a_3 —the ancestor of g_3 at t_{123} —becomes more likely to be a “carrier”, or in other

words, g_3 becomes more likely to be connected to a “carrier” at t_{123} (Fig. 7). Therefore, we consider a pair of conditional probabilities: $P(T_i|C_3)$ and $P(T_i|\overline{C_3})$, where C_3 denotes the event that a_3 is a “carrier” (i.e., g_3 is connected to a "carrier" at t_{123}), $P(T_i|C_3)$ is the probability that gene tree topology T_i occurs given that a_3 is a “carrier”, and $P(T_i|\overline{C_3})$ is the probability that gene tree topology T_i occurs given that a_3 is a “noncarrier” ($i = 1, 2, 3$). In patterns A_2, A_3, A_7 , and A_8 , a_3 is a “carrier” (Fig. 7). Accordingly, $P(T_1|C_3)$ may be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
P(T_1|C_3) &= \sum_{x=2,3,7,8} P(T_1|A_x)P(A_x|C_3) \\
&= \frac{\frac{1}{3}p_1p_2p_3 + P(V_1|V)q_1q_2p_3 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2p_3 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2p_3}{p_1p_2p_3 + q_1q_2p_3 + p_1q_2p_3 + q_1p_2p_3} \\
&= \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2 + P(V_1|V)q_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2
\end{aligned}$$

We have shown that $P(V_1|V) \geq 2/3$ and $P(W_1|W) = 1$. Hence, the above expression becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
P(T_1|C_3) &\geq \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2 + \frac{2}{3}q_1q_2 \\
&= \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{3}q_1 - \frac{1}{3}q_2 + \frac{1}{2}q_1q_2 + \frac{1}{2}q_1q_2 \\
&= \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{2}q_1\left(\frac{1}{3} - p_2\right) + \frac{1}{2}q_2\left(\frac{1}{3} - p_1\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

According expression (7), if $p_1 < 1/3$ and $p_2 < 1/3$ (as shown above, almost always satisfied), $P(T_1|C_3) > \frac{1}{3}$.

On the other hand, in patterns A_1, A_4, A_5 , and A_6 , a_3 is a “noncarrier” (Fig. 7). By applying the total probability theorem, $P(T_1|\overline{C_3})$ can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
P(T_1|\overline{C}_3) &= \sum_{x=1,4,5,6} P(T_1|A_x)P(A_x|\overline{C}_3) \\
&= \frac{\frac{1}{3}q_1q_2q_3 + \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1p_2q_3 + \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]p_1q_2q_3 + P(W_1|W)p_1p_2q_3}{q_1q_2q_3 + q_1p_2q_3 + p_1q_2q_3 + p_1p_2q_3} \\
&= \frac{1}{3}q_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 + P(W_1|W)p_1p_2
\end{aligned}$$

Again, we have shown that $P(V_1 | V) \geq 2/3$ and $P(W_1 | W) = 1$. Hence, the above expression becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
P(T_1|\overline{C}_3) &\leq \frac{1}{3}q_1q_2 + \frac{1}{6}q_1p_2 + \frac{1}{6}p_1q_2 + p_1p_2 \\
&= \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{6}(p_1 + p_2) + p_1p_2 \\
&= \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{2}p_1\left(p_2 - \frac{1}{3}\right) + \frac{1}{2}p_2\left(p_1 - \frac{1}{3}\right) \tag{8}
\end{aligned}$$

According to expression (8), if $p_1 < 1/3$ and $p_2 < 1/3$ (as shown above, almost always satisfied), $P(T_1|\overline{C}_3) < \frac{1}{3}$. Because $P(T_1|C_3) > \frac{1}{3}$ and $P(T_1|\overline{C}_3) < \frac{1}{3}$, it is expected that as p_3 increases (i.e., g_3 becomes more likely to be connected to a ‘‘carrier’’ at t_{123}), T_1 becomes more likely to occur. This conclusion is the same as that drawn by analyzing $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3}$.

In fact, the expression for $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3}$ may be rearranged as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3} &= -\frac{1}{3}q_1q_2 + \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2 \\
&\quad + P(V_1|V)q_1q_2 - \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 - \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 \\
&\quad - P(W_1|W)p_1p_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 \\
&= \frac{1}{3}p_1p_2 + P(V_1|V)q_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 + \left[\frac{1-P(W_1|W)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{3}q_1q_2 - \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]q_1p_2 - \left[\frac{1-P(V_1|V)}{2}\right]p_1q_2 - P(W_1|W)p_1p_2 \\
&= P(T_1|C_3) - P(T_1|\overline{C}_3)
\end{aligned}$$

An increase in p_3 can be understood as a process where a fraction of gene trees with a ‘‘noncarrier’’ a_3 are replaced by a fraction of gene trees with a ‘‘carrier’’ a_3 . In this fraction of

gene trees, as gene trees with a "noncarrier" a_3 are replaced by gene trees with a "carrier" a_3 , the probability of occurrence of gene tree topology T_1 will change from $P(T_1|\overline{C_3})$ to $P(T_1|C_3)$. When this gene tree replacement process is expressed in mathematical language, it is the expression presented above. Therefore, the analysis of $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3}$ and the analysis of $P(T_1|\overline{C_3})$ and $P(T_1|C_3)$ are essentially equivalent. Clarifying the equivalence between the analysis of $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3}$ and the analysis of $P(T_1|\overline{C_3})$ and $P(T_1|C_3)$ help better understand the biological meaning of the expression for $\frac{\partial P(T_1)}{\partial p_3}$, $\frac{\partial P(T_2)}{\partial p_3}$ and $\frac{\partial P(T_3)}{\partial p_3}$ can be similarly understood by decomposing them into $P(T_2|\overline{C_3})$ and $P(T_2|C_3)$, and into $P(T_3|\overline{C_3})$ and $P(T_3|C_3)$, respectively.

Reference

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Figure S1

Supplementary Figure S1. A. A comparison of simulation results of different levels of scaling. The result in the left side was generated with parameters identical to that shown in Figure 5F, the result in the right side was generated using 5-fold larger population sizes, a 5-fold lower selection coefficient, and a 5-fold lower mutation rate (i.e. using a scaling factor that is 1/5 of that of Fig. 5F). These results are similar. Each simulation result shown here only contains $3000 \times 20 = 60,000$ gene trees (in Fig. 5, each contains $6000 \times 20 = 120,000$). Therefore, the variation among replicates is greater than that in Figure 5.

Figure S2

A

```

1 early()
{
  sim.addSubpop("p1", 10000);
}
//first split at generation 200000
200000 early()
{
  sim.addSubpopSplit("p2", 10000, p1);
}
//second split at generation 200100
200100 early()
{
  sim.addSubpopSplit("p3", 400, p2);
}

280100 late() {
  sim.treeSeqOutput(0); //outputfile path
}

```


B

Supplementary Figure S2. A. The species tree set in the simulations of Vanderpool et al. (2020). The left side shows the SLiM codes used by Vanderpool et al. (2020). These codes correspond to the species tree shown on the right side. This species tree is not comparable to any of those used by He et al. (2020). Please compare the species tree shown here and that shown in Figure 5. Additionally, each locus in Vanderpool et al.'s simulations has 4^{1000} possible allelic states, whereas each locus in the simulations of He et al. (2020) is biallelic. Because of these differences, Vanderpool et al.'s simulations cannot be used to examine the replicability of the simulation results of He et al. (2020). Among the differences mentioned above, the most crucial difference lies in N_{123} . The population sizes used by Vanderpool et al. (2020) are in the ratio $N_{12} : N_{123} : N_1 : N_2 : N_3 = 25:25:1:25:25$, whereas the population sizes used by He et al. (2020) are in the ratio $N_{12} : N_{123} : N_1 : N_2 : N_3 = 5:5:1:25:25$. That is to say, the N_{123} used by Vanderpool et al. (2020) is effectively 5 times greater than that used by He et al. (2020). Consequently, the scaled selection coefficient in ancestral species S_{123} (σ_{123}) in Vanderpool et al.'s simulations has an absolute value 5 times greater than that in the simulations of He et al. (2020) (7.5 versus 1.5). Because of this difference, in Vanderpool et al.'s simulations, deleterious mutations occurring in ancestral species S_{123} have a much lower probability of being present in extant species S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 . In such a situation, the ancestries of g_1 , g_2 , and g_3 are often traced back to three identical ancestors. It is unsurprising that asymmetry in gene tree distribution is not pronounced in such a situation. In reality, slightly deleterious mutations have a chance of being present in species S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 . Therefore, the simulation settings used by Vanderpool et al. (2020) are not realistic.

B. We changed the population sizes used by Vanderpool et al. (2020) to those used by He et al. (2020). Other settings used by Vanderpool et al. (2020) remained unchanged. This change in population sizes causes a change in the distribution of gene tree topologies. Such a phenomenon contradicts Vanderpool et al.'s claim "there should be no effect of negative selection on the distribution of tree topologies".

Figure S3

Supplementary Figure S3. The values of $P(V_1|V)$ under neutral evolution and under purifying selection. Under neutral evolution, the observed values of $P(V_1|V)$ agree with the theoretical expectation described in the main text, $P(V_1|V) = 2/3$. Under purifying selection, the observed values of $P(V_1|V)$ are slightly greater than $2/3$. The result of the Mann–Whitney U test suggests that the difference between the values of $P(V_1|V)$ under neutral evolution and those under purifying selection is statistically significant ($p=5.2 \times 10^{-5}$). This phenomenon can be understood as follows: under purifying selection, “noncarriers” tend to produce more offspring in comparison with under neutral evolution. The necessary condition for the occurrence of V_1 genealogical trees is that a “noncarrier” produce more than one offspring. Therefore, under purifying selection, it is expected that V_1 genealogical trees have a greater probability of occurrence in comparison with under neutral evolution. In addition, this phenomenon can be understood by the ancestral selection graph (ASG) model. In the ASG model, the influence of selection is represented by “incoming branches”. The presence of incoming branches can cause a proportion of type W_1 genealogical trees to be transformed into type V_1 genealogical trees. Therefore, the value of $P(V_1|V)$ is expected to increase under purifying selection.